

Black-box and surrogate optimization for tuning spiking neural models of striatum plasticity

https :

[//doi.org/10.3389/fninf.2022.1017222](https://doi.org/10.3389/fninf.2022.1017222)

N.C. Cruz¹, A. González-Redondo^{1,*}, J.L. Redondo², J.A. Garrido¹, E.M. Ortigosa¹ and P.M. Ortigosa²

¹*Dept. of Computer Engineering, Automation and Robotics, University of Granada, Granada, Spain*

²*Dept. of Informatics, University of Almería, ceiA3 Excellence Agri-food Campus, Almería, Spain*

Correspondence*:
A. González-Redondo
alvarogr@ugr.es

2 ABSTRACT

3 The basal ganglia (BG) is a brain structure that has long been proposed to play an essential
4 role in action selection, and theoretical models of spiking neurons have tried to explain how the
5 BG solves this problem. A recently proposed functional and biologically inspired network model
6 of the striatum (an important nucleus of the BG) is based on spike-timing-dependent eligibility
7 (STDE) and captures important experimental features of this nucleus. The model can recognize
8 complex input patterns and consistently choose rewarded actions to respond to such sensory
9 inputs. However, model tuning is challenging due to two main reasons. The first is the expert
10 knowledge required, resulting in tedious and potentially biased trial-and-error procedures. The
11 second is the computational cost of assessing model configurations (approximately 1.78 hours
12 per evaluation). This work studies how to address the model tuning problem through numerical
13 optimization. Considering the cost of assessing solutions, the selected methods stand out due to
14 their low requirements for solution evaluations and compatibility with high-performance computing.
15 They are the SurrogateOpt solver of Matlab and the RBFOpt library, both based on radial basis
16 function approximations, and DIRECT-GL, an enhanced version of the widespread black-box
17 optimizer DIRECT. Besides, a parallel random search serves as a baseline reference of the
18 outcome of opting for sophisticated methods. SurrogateOpt turns out to be the best option for
19 tuning this kind of model. It outperforms, on average, the quality of the configuration found by
20 an expert and works significantly faster and autonomously. RBFOpt and the random search
21 share the second position, but their average results are below the option found by hand. Finally,
22 DIRECT-GL follows this line becoming the worst-performing method.

23 **Keywords:** striatum, reinforcement learning, spiking neural network, dopamine, spike-timing-dependent plasticity, model tuning,
24 surrogate optimization, black-box optimization

1 INTRODUCTION

25 Computational models of the brain are useful tools for studying learning mechanisms. However, the
26 difficulty involved in finding parameters that provide good solutions is a major challenge.

27 A model already published in a previous article (Gonzalez-Redondo et al., 2022) is a complex model
28 that is difficult to obtain good solutions for. This model tries to better understand how learning through
29 interaction to achieve a goal is solved by animals (or agents) by choosing among many possible actions to
30 obtain rewards, as described in the reinforcement learning (RL) paradigm (Sutton et al., 1992). The model
31 is based on spike-timing-dependent eligibility (Gurney et al., 2015) (STDE), a learning rule capturing
32 important experimental features in the brain and, specifically the basal ganglia (BG, a set of nuclei located
33 in the forebrain). This brain structure is related with the process of action-selection, according to biological
34 (Grillner et al., 2005; Graybiel, 1998; Hikosaka et al., 2000) and computational studies (Gurney et al.,
35 2001; Tomkins et al., 2014; Redgrave et al., 1999). We implemented (Gonzalez-Redondo et al., 2022) a
36 functional and biologically inspired network model of the striatum (STR, an important input nucleus of
37 the BG), where learning is based on STDE. The proposed model has been demonstrated to be capable of
38 recognizing input patterns relevant to the task and consistently choosing rewarded actions in response to
39 that input.

40 However, models require tuning (Martínez-Álvarez et al., 2016; Van Geit et al., 2007), and the quality
41 expectations, datasets, and adaptability requirements are continuously growing (Masoli et al., 2020;
42 Van Geit et al., 2008). The model described in (Gonzalez-Redondo et al., 2022), which attracts the attention
43 of this work, contains dozens of free parameters: learning kernel shapes, synaptic and neuron time constants,
44 lateral inhibition weight, etc. Some of them can be inferred from experimental data, but most of them must
45 be manually tuned with plausible values. With this number of parameters, the curse of dimensionality
46 leads to a tedious trial-and-error search procedure prone to failures. Another problem is the computational
47 cost of evaluating each model configuration: it takes approximately 1.78 hours per evaluation in a modern
48 laptop using a single CPU core. Both made the tuning of our model slow (the parameters finally used were
49 found after two months of search), sub-optimal (as there are a huge parametric space not covered) and
50 biased (by the intuition of the expert). Fortunately, model tuning can be addressed as a global optimization
51 problem. There exist modern frameworks, such as Ray[Tune] (Liaw et al., 2018) and Vizier (Golovin et al.,
52 2017), which implement multiple algorithms compatible with this purpose. Besides, the current increase in
53 computer power that allows for defining more sophisticated models also helps us to face more challenging
54 optimization problems (Cruz et al., 2021; Marín et al., 2021; Van Geit et al., 2008).

55 When addressing model tuning as an optimization problem, the objective function generally represents
56 the difference between the desired and achieved output of the model for any candidate configuration.
57 Concerning the associated problem, when the objective function exhibits mathematically exploitable
58 properties, such as linearity, convexity, and continuous variables, it can be exactly solved. Otherwise, its
59 resolution can be significantly challenging (Lindfield and Penny, 2017; Salhi, 2017). This issue might arise
60 when the objective function does not have a closed analytical form or relies on sophisticated models with
61 non-linear expressions, uncertainty, and simulations (Cruz et al., 2018; Marín et al., 2021). Luckily, some
62 methods aim at finding acceptable results with a reasonable effort by using randomness and intuitive ideas.
63 Most heuristics and meta-heuristics would fall into this group (Lindfield and Penny, 2017; Salhi, 2017).
64 Similarly, if a method does not have specific knowledge or strict requirements for the objective function
65 apart from being able to evaluate candidate solutions, it is classified as a black-box optimizer (Audet and
66 Hare, 2017; Golovin et al., 2017). Both categories are frequently linked, as many meta-heuristics, such as
67 evolutionary and swarm intelligence algorithms, are also black-box methods.

68 In this context, black-box optimization methods can be classified into two groups: those without specific
69 components to require few function evaluations and those with them. It could be said that needing few
70 function evaluations to converge is one of the goals pursued when designing any optimization method.
71 However, most population-based meta-heuristics need numerous function evaluations (Costa and Nannicini,
72 2018) to compensate their instability due to randomness (Jones and Martins, 2021). They would hence
73 fall into the first group. For instance, for the successful evolutionary optimizer UEGO (Cruz et al., 2018;
74 García-Martínez et al., 2015; Marín et al., 2021), a robust configuration could need up to 1,000,000 function
75 evaluations (Ortigosa et al., 2001). This potential requirement is usually attenuated with parallel computing,
76 which fits well with population-based algorithms (Cruz et al., 2019; Jelásity, 2013; Storn and Price, 1997).
77 This can be seen as a brute-force approach to tackle the high consumption of function evaluations. The
78 methods in the second group do not renounce the benefits of high-performance computing, but they try
79 to avoid function evaluations by design. Their use can be the only option when the cost of evaluating the
80 objective function cannot be hidden with parallel computing. The most relevant methods in this group are
81 surrogate optimizers (Bhosekar and Ierapetritou, 2018; Costa and Nannicini, 2018; Vu et al., 2017), which
82 avoid evaluating the real objective function by constructing a lightweight model of it. They define an active
83 research line in Global Optimization.

84 In this work, the objective function is not a plain mathematical function, such as a parabola. Instead, each
85 evaluation launches a process that consists in building the neural network according to the input parameters
86 of the candidate configuration, training it, and returning its performance at the target task. As mentioned
87 above, this process is computationally demanding. For this reason, this work pays attention to optimization
88 algorithms requiring few function evaluations. The selection consists of four solvers in total. The first two
89 are SurrogateOpt, provided by the official Global Optimization Toolbox of Matlab (López, 2014), and
90 RBFOpt (Costa and Nannicini, 2018), open-source and written in Python. Both construct a surrogate of
91 the real objective function by combining radial basis ones (Gutmann, 2001; Regis and Shoemaker, 2007).
92 The third method is DIRECT-GL (Stripinis et al., 2018), an enhanced version of the widespread DIRECT
93 (Jones and Martins, 2021), which stands out due to its deterministic and effective strategy of dividing the
94 search space and prioritizing the most promising areas to save function evaluations. The last one is a simple
95 random search (Cruz et al., 2018), which is expected to define the baseline performance. Nonetheless, this
96 method has also been implemented to benefit from parallel computing, so its rate of candidate solution
97 evaluation is high. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the tuning of spiking neural models of striatum
98 plasticity has not been studied from this perspective before. Hence, the ultimate goal of this research is
99 to recommend the most effective strategy for this purpose to save tedious trial-and-error procedures and
100 hyper-parameter tuning for Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) by hand in general, which is inherently
101 biased by the expert.

102 The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes materials and methods. Section 3
103 contains the experimentation and results. Finally, Section 4 shows the conclusions and states future work.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

104 This section starts with a detailed description of the computational models that define the agent behavior
105 and the task it is solving. After that, the four optimization strategies considered are explained.

106 2.1 Computational models

107 For the network model we used conductance-based versions of the Leaky-Integrate and Fire (LIF) neuron
108 model (Gerstner and Kistler, 2002). LIF model simplifies many aspects of neuronal dynamics, so it is

109 more computationally efficient than other commonly used neural models in SNNs. We use this model in
110 every layer of the network. Before the use of optimization methods, the parameters were manually tuned
111 to obtain reasonable firing rates (see details in Supplementary Materials). The STR neurons are divided
112 in D1 or D2 populations, each one with different learning kernel constants (so they can learn to respond
113 to different situations; more on this later), and also divided by channels (one per action). STR D1 and
114 D2 populations are complementary, as the D1 population tries to learn what action it has to do, while D2
115 population tries to learn what action it has to stop. The action neurons are a population that integrates its
116 channel activity and outputs the agent's behavior, and they are tuned to fire every input cycle if they receive
117 enough stimulation (at least two more spikes from D1 neurons than D2 neurons each cycle). The dopamine
118 neuron was tuned to have a firing range from 50 to 350 spikes per second, with these unrealistic values
119 chosen to improve computational performance (instead of simulating a bigger dopaminergic population).

120 The input generation procedure is described in Gonzalez-Redondo et al. (2022) and based on Masquelier
121 et al. (2009); Garrido et al. (2016). The agent perceives the environment as 2000 analog inputs. These inputs
122 are fed one-to-one to an input layer of LIF neurons as currents (Figure 1B), altogether with an oscillatory
123 drive. This oscillatory drive leads to a current-to-phase conversion: the neurons that receive the strongest
124 analog input currents will fire first during the phase of the cycle (Masquelier et al., 2009). This way we
125 encode analog inputs in specific spatio-temporal spike activity patterns. This is called phase-of-firing
126 encoding and represents information in the spike times of neurons relative to the phase of a background
127 oscillation (in our case, the oscillatory drive). New input stimuli are presented at uniformly distributed
128 random intervals of 200-500ms. The stimulus can be a repeating pattern or noise, and both are generated
129 randomly depending on the simulation seed. When presenting a repeating pattern, only half of the input
130 neurons (1000) are pattern-specific, while the other half receives random current values. When no pattern
131 is presented, all the input neurons receive random current values.

132 The network model (Figure 1A) contains two channels. Every channel contains two parallel layers (STR
133 D1 and D2 neurons, respectively) of striatal-like neurons with asymmetrical structured lateral inhibition (as
134 in Burke et al. (2017)) within and between STR D1 and D2 populations. The output of each channel is an
135 action node that integrates the channel activity to decide if the agent takes an action or not. The agent can
136 do none, both, or any of them at a time. A dopaminergic neuron projects its activity to both action channels
137 as a neuromodulator (dopamine) determining what the agent should learn from the recent past experience.
138 An environment reward signal (based on the chosen and the expected action) is delivered to this neuron as
139 excitatory (rewards) or inhibitory (punishments) input.

140 The neurons in each channel receive plastic synapses from the input layer. The STDE (Gurney et al., 2015)
141 learning rule is used, a modification of a reward-modulated STDP learning rule where the kernel constants
142 are dopamine-dependent (that is, different values are defined for low dopamine and high dopamine values,
143 see Figure 2). This rule also uses eligibility traces to store the potential changes, similarly to Izhikevich
144 (2007). The learning kernels are different for STR D1 and D2 neurons, as their biological counterparts
145 respond to different situations (Gerfen and Surmeier, 2011): D1 neurons are more predominant in the direct
146 pathway of the BG, which tend to promote behavior when it is active. D2 neurons are more predominant in
147 the indirect pathway of the BG, which tend to inhibit behavior when it is active. For this reason the initial
148 learning kernels were manually chosen to be complementary: D1 neurons learn to do actions, and D2
149 neurons learn to stop actions. The dopaminergic modulatory signal is global and delivered to every STDE
150 connection from input layer to channel neurons. Lastly, two homeostatic mechanisms are added to improve
151 the learning process: first, the synapses implementing the STDE included a non-Hebbian strengthening in

152 response to every pre-synaptic spike. Second, we include adaptive threshold to our neuron models based on
 153 Galindo et al. (2020).

Figure 1. Cortico-striatal network solving a RL task (from Gonzalez-Redondo et al. (2022)). **A.** Structure of the network. **B-F.** The activity of the network during the last 5 seconds of simulation. Background color indicates the reward policy (yellowish colors, action A is rewarded and B is punished; bluish colors, action B is rewarded and A is punished; grey, any action is punished). **B.** Input pattern conveyed to the input layer. **C.** Raster plot of the channel-A action neurons. Yellow dots represent STR D1 spikes, and orange dots are STR D2 spikes. **D.** Raster plot of channel B. Cyan dots represent STR D1 spikes, and dark blue dots are STR D2 spikes. **E.** Action neuron firing rates. The middle horizontal line represents 0 Hz. Action A and B activity are represented in opposites directions for clarity. Action A neuronal activity increases in yellow zones while action B neuronal activity in cyan intervals. **F.** Firing rate of the dopaminergic neuron (black line). Dotted horizontal lines indicate the range of dopamine activity considered: black is the baseline, green is the maximum reward, and red represents the maximum punishment. Dots indicate rewards (green) and punishment (red) events delivered to the agent. **G.** Evolution of the learning accuracy of the agent, see Section 2.1 for further details. The dotted line marks the accuracy level by chance.

154 The agent has to learn a simple mapping task from stimulus to action. Every 200-500ms a new stimulus
 155 is presented and the agent has to respond with an appropriate action. There are five different repeating
 156 patterns and the agent has two possible actions to choose, A or B. Two patterns require action A, other
 157 two patterns require action B, and the fifth pattern requires do nothing. If the agent responds correctly, the

158 environment gives a reward. If a different action is taken, a punishment is given. If the input is just noise,
159 the environment does not give rewards nor punishments.

160 We use a confusion matrix to help measure the performance of the model. Each row indicates the
161 rewarded action in response to the presented pattern, and each column indicates the selected action in
162 response to the presented pattern. Every cell m_{ij} then counts the number of occurrences of j action being
163 done when i action was expected to be done. We only consider in the calculation those trials in which
164 some reward or punishment can be delivered, ignoring those intervals with only noise as the stimulus.
165 We consider that an action has been taken if the corresponding action neuron has spiked at least once
166 during the pattern presentation, and conversely, we consider that no action has been taken if none of the
167 action neurons spikes during the same duration. By doing so, we obtain a confusion matrix, widely used in
168 classification problems when the objective is to describe the accuracy of a final map process (Stehman,
169 1997). The confusion matrix is defined as in expression (1),

$$C \equiv \begin{bmatrix} m_{11} & m_{12} & \cdots & m_{1C} \\ m_{21} & m_{22} & \cdots & m_{2C} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{C1} & m_{C2} & \cdots & m_{CC} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

170 where m_{ij} represents the number of occurrences belonging to the i -th class (the rewarded action) but
171 classified as members of the j -th class (the selected action).

172 We then measure the model's performance as the accuracy of the classification, defined as the sum of the
173 number of correct predictions (the trace of the matrix) divided by the total number of pattern presentations
174 considered (the sum of the whole matrix). In order to measure the evolution through time of the performance
175 of the models, we calculate the confusion matrix for each pattern presentation and then use a rolling mean
176 of the last 100 values to obtain an estimation of the temporal evolution of the accuracy.

177 2.2 Model tuning as an optimization problem

178 In this context, it is possible to measure the performance of the model resulting from any set of parameters
179 as the accuracy, F , of the classification, according to Equation (2). This value is defined as the sum of the
180 number of correct predictions (the trace of the matrix) divided by the total number of pattern presentations
181 considered (the sum of the whole matrix). To measure the evolution through time of the performance of the
182 models, we calculate the confusion matrix for each pattern presentation and then use a rolling mean of the
183 last 100 values to obtain an estimation of the temporal evolution of the accuracy.

$$F = \frac{\sum_i m_{ii}}{\sum_i \sum_j m_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

184 The value of F will ultimately depend on thirteen variables, a selected subset of all the variables of the
185 model, which determine the model behavior. Notice that the model features inherent stochasticity, which
186 is handled by returning the average of five simulations. The variables are shown in Table 1, including
187 their corresponding ranges. These variables have been chosen to be optimized as they are the ones related
188 to the learning process of the model. We did not optimize the neuron model variables as we already
189 found reasonable values to make their firing behavior match their biological counterparts. Variable w_{max}
190 represents the maximum weight of each plastic synapse. Variable C_{pre} is the homeostatic term applied per

191 presynaptic spike. Variable τ_{th} is the time constant of the adaptive neuron threshold. Variable C_{th} defines the
 192 additive increment of the adaptive threshold of a striatal neuron after a spike, and it is inversely proportional
 193 to the target firing rate. Variable μ is a dimensionless constant that modulates all learning parameters. Lastly,
 194 the kernel shape of the STDE learning rule is defined by the parameters k_{DA}^{SPK} with $SPK \in \{+, -\}$ being
 195 the spike order pre-post for applying k_{DA}^+ and post-pre for applying k_{DA}^- , respectively, and $DA \in \{hi, lo\}$
 196 being the high- or low-DA cases, resulting in four parameters per neuron population: k_{hi}^+ , k_{lo}^+ , k_{hi}^- and k_{lo}^- .
 197 As we have two neuron populations $POP \in \{d1, d2\}$, there are eight k_{POPDA}^{SPK} STDE parameters in total:
 198 k_{d1hi}^+ , k_{d1lo}^+ , k_{d1hi}^- , k_{d1lo}^- , k_{d2hi}^+ , k_{d2lo}^+ , k_{d2hi}^- and k_{d2lo}^- . A graphical representation of all these kernels for
 199 the manually-tuned case can be found in Figure 2.

Table 1. Parameters to tune for the neural model and their allowed ranges.

Variable	Lower bound	Upper bound	Unit
w_{max}	10^{-3}	10^{-1}	μS
C_{pre}	-10^{-5}	10^{-5}	μS
μ	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
τ_{th}	1	200	seconds
C_{th}	10^{-2}	2	mV
k_{d1hi}^+	-1	1	-
k_{d1hi}^-	-1	1	-
k_{d1lo}^+	-1	1	-
k_{d1lo}^-	-1	1	-
k_{d2hi}^+	-1	1	-
k_{d2hi}^-	-1	1	-
k_{d2lo}^+	-1	1	-
k_{d2lo}^-	-1	1	-

200 Based on this quality metric and the variables involved, model tuning can be expressed as an optimization
 201 problem. It focuses on finding the values of the parameters (within their feasible range) that maximize the
 202 value of F , which becomes the objective function in optimization terms. The problem can be formulated
 203 according to Equation (3). For simplicity, only the first and the last variables are shown. The constraints
 204 keep every variable in its feasible range, which results in a box-constrained problem (Costa and Nannicini,
 205 2018; Stripinis and Paulavičius, 2022). The max and min superscripts linked to each parameter symbol
 206 denote its upper and lower bounds, respectively. The numerical values are those shown in Table 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underset{w_{max}, \dots, k_{d2lo}^-}{\text{maximize}} && F(w_{max}, \dots, k_{d2lo}^-) \\
 & \text{subject to} && w_{max}^{lower} \leq w_{max} \leq w_{max}^{upper} \\
 & && \dots \\
 & && k_{d2lo}^{-,lower} \leq k_{d2lo}^- \leq k_{d2lo}^{-,upper}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Figure 2. Manually-tuned kernels used for STDE synapses of MSN D1 (left) and D2 (right), showing the weight change depending on the time difference between pre- and post-synaptic spikes and dopamine. Lines represent kernels at dopamine minimum and maximum values (red and green, respectively).

207 Notice that the problem is defined as a maximization one, but optimization methods traditionally aim
 208 at minimization. Regardless, this is not relevant because converting a maximization problem into a
 209 minimization one is trivial. It is only necessary to multiply the objective function by -1, i.e., maximizing
 210 $F(\dots)$ is equal to minimizing $-F(\dots)$.

211 2.3 Optimization methods

212 As introduced, evaluating the objective function relies on non-deterministic simulations and is
 213 computationally demanding. Thus, the methods considered are designed for black-box optimization
 214 (Audet and Hare, 2017), i.e., RBFOpt (Costa and Nannicini, 2018), SurrogateOpt (Matlab, 2021), DIRECT-
 215 GL (Stripinis et al., 2018), and a random search Cruz et al. (2018). The first three, which are also the
 216 preferred options, have been explicitly designed to require few function evaluations. All of them are
 217 prepared for exploiting parallel computing. Finally, it is relevant to highlight that among the considered
 218 methods, DIRECT-GL is the only deterministic one, which means that the algorithm does not rely on
 219 randomness and always returns the same result for the same problem instance (s) and configuration.

220 2.3.1 RBFOpt

221 RBFOpt, published in Costa and Nannicini (2018), is an open-source library written in Python for
 222 black-box optimization with computationally-expensive objective functions. This tool is based on the
 223 method proposed by Gutmann (2001).

224 RBFOpt belongs to the family of surrogate optimization methods. The fundamental idea of surrogate
 225 optimization is that the process relies on iteratively building an approximate model (response surface or
 226 surrogate model) of the real objective function. While the former approximates the latter, its computational
 227 requirements are expected to be significantly lower, and the accuracy can improve as the information
 228 on the target function increases with the points evaluated (Vu et al., 2017). For building the surrogate

Table 2. Frequent radial basis functions.

$\phi(r)$	Type	Minimum degree
r	Linear	0
r^3	Cubic	1
$r^2 \log r$	Thin plate spline	1

229 model, RBFOpt uses radial basis functions, whose output depends on the distance between the input and a
 230 given reference. In this field, Gutmann (2001) was a pioneer of using radial basis functions for optimizing
 231 computationally demanding black-box functions (Costa and Nannicini, 2018).

232 Let $f(x)$ be an abstract objective function of the form $f : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where $x \in [x^{min}, x^{max}]$, and
 233 $x^{min}, x^{max} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, i.e., the corresponding lower and upper bounds of each decision variable. Notice that
 234 this can be seen as a generalization of the particular problem formulation in Equation (3). For K different
 235 points of the search space, x_1, \dots, x_K , with known values, $y_1 = f(x_1), \dots, y_K = f(x_K)$, the associated
 236 radial basis function interpolant, s_K , has the following structure as the sum of K radial basis functions
 237 (Costa and Nannicini, 2018; Vu et al., 2017):

$$s_K(x) = \sum_{i=1}^K \lambda_i \phi(\|x - x_i\|) + p(x) \quad (4)$$

238 where $\phi : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which is a radial basis function, $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_K \in \mathbb{R}$ acting like weights of the model, and
 239 $p(x)$ is a polynomial. The minimum degree of p to guarantee the existence of the interpolant depends on the
 240 form of ϕ . Table 2 contains three common radial basis functions for a generic input, r . It also includes the
 241 minimum degree of their accompanying polynomial p that ensures the existence of the interpolant. If these
 242 components are appropriately configured, the desired radial basis function interpolant can be efficiently
 243 computed by solving a linear system to find the unknown parameters, such as the weights. For instance,
 244 x_1, \dots, x_K should be pairwise distinct (Costa and Nannicini, 2018; Vu et al., 2017).

245 The general procedure applied by optimization methods using radial basis functions follows Algorithm 1
 246 (Costa and Nannicini, 2018). A particular method will define a strategy to implement these generic steps,
 247 starting from selecting the initial points. For example, for low-dimensional problems, a valid approach is to
 248 choose the corners of the search space. Another one is to pick the corners and the central point. Controlling
 249 the effort put into improving the accuracy of the surrogate model and finding the best point with the current
 250 model is also critical. The method by Gutmann (2001) defined a measure of the bumpiness of the surrogate
 251 model for this purpose. Their method assumes that the real objective function does not oscillate excessively,
 252 so when configuring models and considering new points, the smoother (or ‘least bumpy’) interpolant is
 253 preferred (see Figure 3, which assumes four known points and a hypothetical target value of the cost
 254 function). Regardless, describing these aspects in detail is out of the scope of this paper. See the work by
 255 Vu et al. (2017) to have a detailed overview, and that by Costa and Nannicini (2018) to understand the
 256 fundamentals of RBFOpt.

257 In this context, RBFOpt has two main contributions. The first is an automatic model selection component.
 258 The second is the support for using faster yet less accurate variants of the objective function. The latter is
 259 especially appropriate for the target problem since the simulation-related parts of the objective function,
 260 such as the training time and the seeds, are adjustable. They can be modified by the expert in charge of

Algorithm 1 Generic global optimization through radial basis functions

- 1: Initial step - Select K points
- 2: **while** There is available function evaluations **do**
- 3: Compute the radial basis function interpolant
- 4: Decide between improving the surrogate model and finding the best point using the current model.
- 5: Determine the next point to consider according to the previous decision
- 6: Evaluate the objective function at the new point
- 7: **end while**
- 8: **return** Best point found

Figure 3. Depiction of two surrogate models interpolating four points (blue circles) and reaching a target value (horizontal dashed line). The green solid-line model is considered more likely than the red dashed-line one since it is smoother. In other words, the method by Gutmann (2001) assumes that it is more likely that the point tagged with a diamond exists (green line) rather than that with a square (red line) in the real function (Costa and Nannicini, 2018).

261 model tuning to reduce time at the expense of losing accuracy. These properties, along with its open-source
 262 nature, the compatibility with parallel computing, and the good results reported in Costa and Nannicini
 263 (2018) motivated its consideration for the present work.

264 2.3.2 SurrogateOpt

265 SurrogateOpt is a solver for computationally-demanding black-box optimization problems provided by
 266 the Global Optimization Toolbox (López, 2014) of Matlab Matlab (2021) since its version R2018b. As
 267 introduced, it belongs to the same group as RBFOpt since the method is a surrogate optimization algorithm.
 268 SurrogateOpt also uses radial basis function interpolators. Its documentation motivates this decision by
 269 highlighting that they support any number of dimensions and are computationally cheap to construct,
 270 evaluate, and extend. This tool is mainly based on the algorithm proposed by Regis and Shoemaker (2007).
 271 It has been selected due to its effectiveness, simplicity of use, and compatibility with parallel computing.

272 Conceptually, SurrogateOpt follows a scheme similar to Algorithm 1. The fundamental differences
 273 correspond to the implementation of each step and specific definitions. In this regard, SurrogateOpt has
 274 a rich set of associated concepts and procedures, which are summarized below. According to its official
 275 documentation, the method alternates between two stages: Construct Surrogate and Search for Minimum.
 276 The change between them occurs after what is called the surrogate reset.

277 In the first stage, the method builds a surrogate of the real objective function. For this purpose, it
 278 interpolates a radial basis function through a set of points whose value must be computed with the real
 279 yet computationally demanding objective function. SurrogateOpt uses a cubic radial basis function with

280 a linear tail, which minimizes the concept of bumpiness (Gutmann, 2001) previously mentioned when
 281 describing RBFOpt. In the beginning, the solver computes and evaluates a user-given number of random
 282 points distributed adequately within the bounds. It can also start from a user-given set of points of known
 283 value. In later executions of this stage, the software package will create and evaluate a parameter-defined
 284 number of random points. As explained for RBFOpt, building the desired interpolant involves solving a
 285 linear system of equations.

286 In the second stage, SurrogateOpt looks for a minimum of the objective function using a procedure
 287 that resembles a local search. More specifically, the method defines a search region radius, known as
 288 the scale, whose initial value is 0.2. It starts from the best point since the last surrogate reset, i.e., the
 289 one with the smallest objective function value. This point is called the incumbent point. The search then
 290 focuses on finding a minimum of a merit function that relates the surrogate and the distance from the points
 291 evaluated with the real objective function. This approach aims to find a trade-off between minimizing the
 292 surrogate, which is not the real objective function and is potentially less accurate, and evaluating new
 293 points accurately.

294 Mathematically, the definition of the merit function for any point x combines two weighted terms, the
 295 scaled surrogate, $S(x)$, and the scaled distance, $D(x)$. Being s_{min} and s_{max} the minimum and maximum
 296 surrogate values of the sample points, respectively, and $s(x)$ that of the considered point, the scaled
 297 surrogate is defined as follows (Matlab, 2021):

$$S(x) = \frac{s(x) - s_{min}}{s_{max} - s_{min}} \quad (5)$$

298 $S(x)$ is non-negative and zero at points having minimal surrogate values among sample points. Concerning
 299 the scaled distance, it is defined as follows:

$$D(x) = \frac{d_{max} - d(x)}{d_{max} - d_{min}} \quad (6)$$

300 where d_{min} and d_{max} are the minimum and maximum distances from a sample point to any evaluated one,
 301 respectively, and $d(x)$ is the minimum distance of the point x to an evaluated one. $D(x)$ is non-negative,
 302 and zero at points at the furthest distance from evaluated points. Hence, minimizing $D(x)$ orientates the
 303 algorithm towards regions separated from evaluated points. The merit function is a convex combination of
 304 both parts according to the following structure:

$$wS(x) + (1 - w)D(x) \quad (7)$$

305 where w is a weighting factor between zero and one. The greater it is, the most effort is put into minimizing
 306 the surrogate model. Analogously, the smaller it is, the most interest in exploring new regions. This
 307 weighting factor cycles through the following values, according to Regis and Shoemaker (2007): 0.3, 0.5,
 308 0.8, and 0.95.

309 During the search, the solver adds multiple (up to thousands) random vectors to the incumbent point to
 310 generate sample points. The vectors are shifted and scaled by the bounds in each dimension and ultimately
 311 multiplied by the scale. The sample points must also respect the problem bounds. Then, the merit function
 312 is evaluated at all of them further than a parameter-defined distance from any point previously evaluated.
 313 The one featuring the best (lowest) value of the merit function becomes an adaptive point. The real objective
 314 function will be ultimately computed at it, which will be used to update the surrogate model and assess the

315 real gain from the incumbent value. If the real value of the adaptive point is significantly better than the
316 current incumbent point, the former replaces the latter, and the search is considered successful. Otherwise,
317 the incumbent point remains unaltered, and the search is classified as unsuccessful.

318 The scale of the search changes when one of the following conditions is met:

- 319 1. There have been three successful searches since the last scale change.
- 320 2. There have been either five or the number of problem variables (whichever greater) unsuccessful
321 searches since the last scale change.

322 If the first condition is met, the scale is doubled (up to a maximum length of 0.8 times the size of the box
323 defined by the problem bounds). If the second situation occurs first, the scale is divided by two (without
324 becoming lower than $1e-5$ times the size of the box defined by the problem bounds). By proceeding this
325 way, the search ultimately focuses near an incumbent point featuring a small objective function value.

326 After considering all the new sample points further than a minimum distance from evaluated points, the
327 Search for Minimum phase ends to go back to the Construct Surrogate one, i.e., resetting the surrogate
328 model. This phase change generally occurs after reducing the scale until all sample points are closely
329 around the incumbent point.

330 2.3.3 DIRECT-GL

331 DIRECT-GL, proposed by Stripinis et al. (2018); Stripinis and Paulavičius (2022), is an enhanced version
332 of a popular method, DIRECT (Jones and Martins, 2021). This new variant is designed as a modification
333 of a specific part of the original method. Hence, it is convenient to start by describing the initial DIRECT
334 and its framework, inherited by the new one.

335 DIRECT was proposed in Jones et al. (1993) as a modification of Lipschitzian Optimization that did
336 not require specifying a Lipschitz constant, i.e., a bound on the rate of change of the objective function,
337 which cannot be easily computed in real problems (or it may not exist). Aside from keeping a deterministic
338 behavior, the method was simpler, converged faster, and featured a certain degree of compatibility with
339 parallel computing. It was later revised by his author in Jones (2001) to handle not only box or domain
340 constraints and continuous variables, but also nonlinear inequality constraints and integer variables. From
341 the beginning, this method was conceived for black-box optimization and situations in which the objective
342 function was time-consuming.

343 Global optimization algorithms must find a trade-off between exploration and exploitation of the search
344 space (Van Geit et al., 2008). The first term refers to finding unexplored regions, and the second represents
345 the capacity to find the best solution in a known zone (global and local search capabilities, respectively).
346 In Lipschitz Optimization, the Lipschitz constant is treated as a weighting factor determining how much
347 emphasis to put into global over local search by indicating where to split the search space into sub-regions.
348 This value must equal or exceed the maximum rate of change of the objective function, so conservative
349 configurations excessively focus on global search. It also makes these methods slow to converge because
350 modifying the value at search is challenging. In contrast to them, DIRECT could maintain the scheme of
351 dividing the search space and autonomously prioritized the regions to explore by virtually considering all
352 possible constants. The division was also independent of the number of dimensions, so the algorithm was
353 more scalable with the problem dimensionality (yet not recommended for more than 20 variables (Jones,
354 2001)).

Figure 4. Main aspects of DIRECT and its search space after two iterations. At the beginning of the initial iteration, point A is the first evaluated and represents the first and only rectangle (square) defined by the search space. It is trisected and results in the rectangles defined by points B and C. At the second iteration, the rectangle defined by point C is selected and trisected resulting in rectangles defined by points D and E.

355 More specifically, DIRECT starts by normalizing each variable to $[0, 1]$ so that the search space becomes
 356 the unit hypercube. Then, the method proceeds by dividing it into sub-rectangles. This scheme determines
 357 the name of the method, since DIRECT comes from ‘DIViding RECTangles’. The rectangles are represented
 358 by the value of the objective function at their center, which avoids the effect of problem dimensionality:
 359 rectangles only have one center independently of the dimensions. It is also relevant to highlight that the
 360 referred division is a trisection in reality, which allows keeping the focus on the original rectangle without
 361 further re-evaluation, i.e., its center stills refer to a different region. Figure 4 depicts these ideas assuming a
 362 2D search space and two divisions (trisections).

363 The fundamental aspect of DIRECT is how the rectangles are selected for division and further exploration
 364 at each iteration. This selection is deterministic and theoretically considers every possible balance between
 365 exploration and exploitation (Lipschitz-like constant). As detailed in Jones (2001), a pure global method
 366 would always select the widest rectangle. A pure local one would opt for the one with the best value at its
 367 center. The former avoids overlooking the promising regions, while the latter promotes that.

368 DIRECT does not force itself to select just one rectangle, which would require parameters to tune. Instead,
 369 the method computes all the weightings of local versus global search. For this purpose, it defines the size
 370 of any rectangle as the distance between its center and one of its vertices. Then, for every selection at a
 371 particular iteration, the method represents all the available rectangles depending on their size and the value
 372 of their center. After that, it proceeds to select those in the low-right convex hull. Figure 5 depicts this idea
 373 assuming a minimization problem. The selected rectangles are the balanced options between local and
 374 global search considering the central value and size of the corresponding regions. Notice the similitude
 375 of this approach to computing the Pareto set as the solution to a multi-objective optimization problem
 376 (Filatovas et al., 2017).

377 Interestingly, as explained in Jones (2001) and also shown in Figure 5, the selection of rectangles can
 378 be alternatively derived from the rate of change of the function in each. If one knows the optimal value,
 379 anchors a half-line at it, and swings the free extreme upwards, the first dot touched represents the rectangle
 380 with the most reasonable rate of change, i.e., gradual instead of steep, to contain the optimum. Hence, that
 381 rectangle must be selected. In reality, the optimal value is not usually known. However, it is possible to
 382 repeat this process from the best value known so far, as the optimal value will be equal to or lower than it,
 383 to minus infinity. Selecting the touched dot for each anchored point results in the lower-right convex hull
 384 previously defined. It is hence possible to obtain the same selection scheme yet by thinking differently.

Figure 5. Selection of rectangles to further explore (divide) in DIRECT for a hypothetical minimization problem. The available rectangles are represented as dots (circles are shown for clarity). The horizontal axis corresponds to the size of each rectangle, and the vertical one shows the value of the objective function at its center (lower is better for minimization). In this context, rectangle A is the one with the best central value, while B encompasses the broadest region. The rectangles selected will lie in the lower-right convex hull, which represents the optimal balance between exploration and exploitation. The red lines at the bottom shows an alternative way to derive this selection method: A line is anchored at every value better than known, starting from that one minus the desired accuracy (minimum relevant change), ϵ , and swept upwards until reaching a rectangle. Repeating the process to (negative for minimization) infinity results in the same convex hull (and avoids regions with expected negligible improvements).

385 Besides, it is possible to subtract an arbitrary value, ϵ , to the best value known to discard from the hull
 386 the rectangles with negligible improvements. Accordingly, DIRECT only expects as input the maximum
 387 number of function evaluations and the constant ϵ , which can be seen as the desired accuracy of the solution.
 388 The interested reader can see Jones (2001) for further information about this algorithm.

389 Despite its good properties (conceptual simplicity, ingenious deterministic exploration, and requiring a
 390 single parameter), DIRECT is not free of potential drawbacks, and researchers have proposed numerous
 391 variants (Jones and Martins, 2021; Stripinis and Paulavičius, 2022). The two main flaws of the initial
 392 method are (Stripinis and Paulavičius, 2022) i) the potential waste of function evaluations in sub-optimal
 393 regions for functions with many local optima and ii) the slow convergence rate even after having identified
 394 the basin of the global optimum (Jones and Martins, 2021). Accordingly, the method selected for this work
 395 is one of the revised versions of DIRECT, i.e., DIRECT-GL, which tries to overcome both (Stripinis et al.,
 396 2018).

397 For this purpose, the authors of DIRECT-GL modified the selection of rectangles to consider more than its
 398 ancestor. The process has two stages and fits into the original framework without requiring extra parameters.
 399 The first one enhances the global search component of the method, represented by the letter ‘G’ in its name.
 400 It starts by adding the rectangles with the best central value and prioritizing those that are bigger. This
 401 approach results in more rectangles of medium size and the best values. The second phase is similar, but
 402 it considers the Euclidean distance to the best point known so far instead of the objective function value.
 403 Namely, it tries to add more hyper-rectangles close to the current minimum. This strategy strengthens the
 404 exploration of the most promising area, i.e., it enhances the local search aspect of the method, represented
 405 by the letter ‘L’ in its name.

406 Aside from the computational studies in Stripinis et al. (2018), the effectiveness of this strategy is
 407 supported by the recent comparison in Stripinis and Paulavičius (2022), where DIRECT-GL exhibits the

408 best performance among all the DIRECT-based methods. The implementation in Stripinis and Paulavičius
 409 (2022), also used in this work, unifies the results of both stages in a single selection. This aspect differs
 410 from the original work to make the method more suitable for parallelization and more effective.

411 2.3.4 Random Search

412 A pure random search procedure is arguably the simplest global optimizer (Brooks, 1958), and it belongs
 413 to the stochastic family of optimization methods (Cruz et al., 2018). More specifically, it consists in
 414 randomly generating solutions in the search space while keeping a record of the best one found so far.
 415 Algorithm 2 describes this process in detail. Notice that it is expressed in general terms, and the comparison
 416 criterion will depend on if the objective function is to be minimized or maximized.

Algorithm 2 Random search

Require: Objective function: f , Evaluations allowed: $evals$

```

1: solution  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: currentVal  $\leftarrow$  worst value
3: iter  $\leftarrow 0$ 
4: while iter < evals do
5:   point  $\leftarrow$  random()
6:   if  $f(\text{point})$  is better than currentVal then
7:     solution  $\leftarrow$  point
8:     currentVal  $\leftarrow f(\text{point})$ 
9:   end if
10:  iter  $\leftarrow$  iter + 1
11: end while
12: return solution

```

417 Despite its simplicity, this method converges to a global optimum when the number of allowed evaluations
 418 tends to infinity (Brooks, 1958). On the one hand, its practical applicability is low due to the lack of
 419 orientation during the search. For this reason, it has been initially selected for the problem at hand
 420 as the expected baseline reference, especially considering that the computational cost of the objective
 421 function makes it difficult to work with high evaluation budgets. Thus, the previous methods are expected
 422 to outperform this one because of their sophisticated components to explore and exploit the search
 423 space (Van Geit et al., 2008). On the other hand, the simple structure of this procedure, which is also
 424 embarrassingly parallel in terms of high-performance computing (Trobec et al., 2018), ensures a high
 425 rate of solution evaluations in an appropriate computing platform. Hence, its results can be of interest
 426 depending on the ultimate problem difficulty and the quality requirements.

3 EXPERIMENTATION AND RESULTS

427 3.1 Problem-specific setup and reference value

428 A sample tuning problem of a spiking neural model of striatum plasticity has been addressed to assess
 429 the performance of the considered optimization methods. The problem was selected due to its high number
 430 of parameters, biological relevance, and computational cost of evaluating solutions. The model details are
 431 in (Gonzalez-Redondo et al., 2022), and the important problem-specific setup is summarized below.

432 The simulation time was 500 seconds, enough to the hand-tuned models to converge to a solution. The
 433 model contains 2000 leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) input neurons and 16 spiking LIF output neurons
 434 with adaptive threshold divided in two channels (one per possible action). During the learning protocol 5

435 different repeating stimuli were used, besides noise. The duration of each stimulus is taken from a uniform
436 random distribution between 100 and 500ms. Five different random seeds were used for every set of
437 parameters tested and the resulting fitness of each seed averaged.

438 The best result obtained without optimization methods is shown in Figure 1. Panels C-F show network
439 activity and rewards/punishments during the last 5 seconds of simulation. The most relevant information
440 is the accuracy through the training process. The mean of the last 100 seconds of the accuracy is used as
441 the fitness for the objective function. The procedure to calculate the accuracy is described in section 2.1.
442 The accuracy evolution of the best result obtained by an expert after manually tuning for two months the
443 parameters using a trial-and-error procedure is shown in Figure 1G. Good sets of parameters typically
444 plateau after 400 seconds, as wrong actions are taken from time to time even with further training.

445 3.2 Computational setup

446 The computational platform used belongs to the high-performance computing cluster of the
447 Supercomputing – Algorithms research group from the University of Almería, Spain. Specifically, up to
448 8 Bull Sequana X440-A5 nodes were used to launch different executions. Every node features 2 AMD
449 EPYC Rome 7642 with 48 cores each, i.e., 96 cores in total, 512 GB of RAM, and 240 GB SSD as its
450 main disk. In a core of one of these nodes, evaluating a candidate solution or set of model parameters for
451 the configuration described above takes 1.78 ± 0.12 hours on average. This value has been computed by
452 generating and evaluating 96 random feasible parameter sets. The software environment consists of Matlab
453 2020b for SurrogateOpt, DIRECT-GL, and Random Search, and Python 3.6.8 for RBFOpt.

454 Two computational budgets have been considered, 300 and 600 function evaluations. The first results
455 from taking into account the estimated run time as follows: Since each evaluation takes 1.78 hours on
456 average using a high-end processor, 300 evaluations should take $300 \times 1.78 = 534$ hours at least, i.e., 22
457 days approximately. This estimation assumes a sequential execution workflow, as a human expert will
458 likely proceed, and neglects the overhead associated with the internal computations of the optimizers. The
459 value of 22 days of work is in the same order of magnitude as the most favorable conditions found by the
460 authors of this paper when doing the referred model fitting by hand. Similarly, the value of 300 function
461 evaluations is equal to the budget used by RBFOpt by default. Concerning the second limit used, 600,
462 it has been adjusted to two times the lower value. By proceeding this way, it will be possible to assess
463 the benefits of doubling the effort. This value would also be close to the maximum function evaluations
464 that Surrogateopt would assign to the problem at hand, namely, $50 \times 13 = 650$ according to the official
465 documentation.

466 The sequential run time estimations would be 22 and 44 days, approximately. The former, for 300
467 evaluations, is demanding, but the latter, for 600, starts to be overwhelming for a person. Nevertheless,
468 when automating the process by using optimizers compatible with parallel computing and there is access to
469 a cluster, both conditions met in this work, the run time can be significantly lower. Ideally, by deploying
470 96 threads, the objective function evaluation time could be reduced by a factor up to 96. This speedup
471 would mean turning the 534 hours turn into 5.56, approximately. In general, perfect speedup is achieved
472 rarely. Spawning and managing concurrent execution units comes at a cost, sequential tasks do not benefit
473 from them, and there might not always be enough work for all (e.g., few hyper-rectangles selected by
474 DIRECT-GL at a particular iteration). Regardless, the time taken by the optimizers in the cluster is expected
475 to be significantly lower than estimated above for a sequential execution.

476 Apart from controlling the number of function evaluations allowed, the four solvers have been configured
477 with their default options. This includes configuring RBFOpt to use the Bonmin (Bonami et al., 2008)

478 and Ipopt (Wächter and Biegler, 2006) solvers (Costa and Nannicini, 2018) for addressing the internal
479 sub-problems that arise (e.g., adjusting the radial basis function interpolants). Aside from this, notice that
480 RBFOpt stands out by being capable of using a less accurate yet faster version of the objective function.
481 Working with it requires both the referred kind of function and the lower and upper bounds of the expected
482 error. To accelerate the neural model assessment, i.e., the objective function, the number of simulation
483 seeds has been reduced from 5 to 1, which should make its computation five times faster on average.

484 The inaccuracy estimation has been computed as follows: 8 cluster nodes with the same specifications as
485 defined above were used to generate 26880 feasible configurations randomly. Then, the standard deviation
486 of the objective value for each one of the five simulation seeds was recorded. The average standard deviation
487 between seeds for the same configuration was approximately 0.03. Then, according to the empirical rule
488 of Statistics, this average standard deviation was multiplied by 3 to cover 99.7% of the values assuming
489 a standard distribution. The result is 0.09, which was ultimately rounded up to 0.10 to add an arbitrary
490 extra margin. Accordingly, the inaccurate yet faster function is passed to RBFOpt considering that the real
491 value (if 5 simulation seeds were considered instead of 1) will be in the range of ± 0.10 plus the inaccurate
492 estimation.

493 3.3 Numerical results

494 Table 3 contains the results for the model tuning problem addressed with each optimizer and function
495 evaluation budget. The first column shows the optimization algorithm. The second one displays the number
496 of function evaluations allowed. The values generally refer to the standard function with five simulation
497 seeds. However, the two last cases of RBFOpt combine the full function with the one featuring a single
498 simulation seed to be faster despite reducing its accuracy. They include the word ‘fast’ to highlight this
499 aspect. Notice that dividing the fast term by 5 and adding it to the standard one results in the same budgets
500 considered, i.e., 300 and 600 standard function evaluations. In the beginning, the second configuration
501 of this type for RBFOpt consisted of 400 complete evaluations and up to 1000 fast ones, but the results
502 were worst, and the solver opted for not executing that many fast evaluations. Thus, it seems preferable to
503 put more emphasis on complete ones even though the estimated cost is theoretically equivalent, and we
504 ultimately chose the configuration shown.

505 The following two columns contain the average efficiency (higher is better, with the best value in bold
506 font) and the standard deviation for each optimizer and configuration. All the stochastic methods have
507 been independently executed 20 times. With this information, the 95% confidence intervals have been
508 computed according to the t-Student distribution considering the sample sizes (i.e., under 30 records
509 each). They are shown in the fifth column. The sixth and last column contains the average run time
510 for each case (the standard deviations are omitted because of not being either significant or especially
511 relevant for this variable). For DIRECT-GL, the run times have been obtained by launching 8 independent
512 executions, one per available node. Finally, it is relevant to mention that the RandomSearch results have
513 been obtained from the dataset with 26880 random points used to assess the accuracy of the fast version of
514 the objective function. More specifically, they come from taking 20 random samples with as many instances
515 as the function evaluation budget. Thus, the run times of this method have been analytically estimated by
516 multiplying the average evaluation time by the computational budget. They have been ultimately divided
517 by the number of CPU cores due to the embarrassingly parallel nature of the process.

518 Concerning the results, the most noticeable aspect is that DIRECT-GL shows the worst performance in
519 terms of achieved fitness and required run time. The aptitude of its solutions for 300 and 600 function
520 evaluations is even worse than that obtained with the simplest method, i.e., RandomSearch. Both results,

Table 3. Performance metrics for each optimizer and configuration considered computed with the results of 20 independent executions.

Optimizer	Function evaluations	Average fitness	Standard Deviation	Confidence Interval (95%)	Average run time (h)
SurrogateOpt	300	0.7269	0.0667	[0.6957, 0.7581]	6.07
	600	0.7699	0.0691	[0.7376, 0.8022]	11.26
RBFOpt	300	0.5325	0.1461	[0.4641, 0.6009]	6.85
	600	0.6267	0.1434	[0.5596, 0.6938]	13.27
	200 + 500 fast	0.5843	0.1458	[0.5161, 0.6525]	5.30
	500 + 500 fast	0.5923	0.1550	[0.5198, 0.6648]	12.29
DIRECT-GL	300	0.4165	-	[0.4165]	81.98
	600	0.4618	-	[0.4618]	103.38
Random Search	300	0.5492	0.1412	[0.4831, 0.6153]	5.56
	600	0.6159	0.1027	[0.5678, 0.6640]	11.13

521 i.e., 0.4165 and 0.4618, stay outside of the confidence interval of this stochastic method, and below the
522 lower bounds for 300 and 600 function evaluations. The same occurs when considering RBFOpt and its
523 configuration with 300 evaluations. Accordingly, the difference between these methods is statistically
524 significant. Its average run time is also significantly higher than the rest, which comes from the fact that the
525 parallelism of DIRECT-GL is strictly bounded by the number of selected rectangles at any point. For this
526 reason, it will not always exploit all the available CPU cores, which is critical in the context of interest.

527 Conversely, SurrogateOpt stands out as the best-performing method in terms of achieved fitness and a
528 low standard deviation. The lower bound of its lowest confidence interval does not fall into the range of
529 any other one, so the observed difference between these optimization strategies for the target problem is
530 significant. Besides, considering that the run time of RandomSearch is an optimistic approximation, it
531 could be said that the computational performance is virtually equivalent. Accordingly, the direct conclusion
532 that can be drawn from the results shown in Table 3 is that SurrogateOpt is the best solver for this kind of
533 model tuning problem. Moreover, its average results are comparable to that obtained by an expert after
534 a tedious and time-demanding model tuning process. More specifically, as detailed in Section 3.1, the
535 fitness of the expert-based model tuning was 0.7216, while the average of SurrogateOpt is 0.7269 with 300
536 function evaluations only. Nevertheless, one can doubt the effectiveness of doubling the computational
537 budget for SurrogateOpt because the confidence intervals of both cases overlap.

538 When confidence intervals do not overlap, the difference between two groups is statistically significant.
539 However, when they do, the difference might still be relevant Goldstein and Healy (1995); Sullivan (2008).
540 To avoid this uncertainty, the confidence intervals for their difference will be computed. For this purpose,
541 as both samples have less than 30 instances, the t-Student distribution will be used again. Notice that the
542 following formulation assumes similar variances in the population, as it occurs between both cases of
543 SurrogateOpt. The pooled estimate of the common standard deviation, S_P is computed as follows:

$$S_P = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)\sigma_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)\sigma_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}} \quad (8)$$

544 where n_1 and n_2 are the sample sizes of groups 1 and 2, respectively, and σ_1 and σ_2 refer to their
545 corresponding standard deviation. With this information, the confidence interval for the difference between
546 two means, \bar{x}_1 and \bar{x}_2 , is obtained as follows:

$$(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2) \pm tSP \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}} \quad (9)$$

547 where t refers to the appropriate value from the t-Student table (determined by the sample sizes, as
548 introduced) for the desired confidence level and $n_1 + n_2 - 2$ degrees of freedom. Notice that the two terms
549 after t define the standard error of the difference in means between \bar{x}_1 and \bar{x}_2 .

550 Back to the mean and standard deviations of both configurations of SurrogateOpt, the 95% confidence
551 interval of their difference is [-0.0865, 0.0005] according to 9. It defines a range of likely values for the
552 difference in means between both cases, $\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2$, where \bar{x}_1 is that of 300 function evaluations and \bar{x}_2 is that
553 of 600. Theoretically, since the interval contains the null value, i.e., 0, it can be concluded that there is
554 no statistically significant difference between the average results of launching SurrogateOpt with 300 and
555 600 function evaluations. Even if the upper bound of this interval were slightly below zero, the average
556 difference could be perceived as negligible yet confirmed. That said, in practical terms, since the outcome
557 of this process is a model parameter set with the highest possible fitness, it seems reasonable to work with
558 600 function evaluations and several independent runs whenever possible.

559 Regarding RBFOpt and RandomSearch, they remain between the best performing solver, SurrogateOpt,
560 and the worst, DIRECT-GL. Being free to use without cost, unlike SurrogateOpt, is their main attribute
561 in this context. It is hard to find the best option among them at a glance due to the significant overlap
562 and comparatively high standard deviations. Technically, RBFOpt offers the best average results when
563 allowed to execute 600 function evaluations. Besides, the 95% confidence interval of the difference between
564 300 and 600 function evaluations confirms the effectiveness of doubling the computational effort, yet it
565 is arguably negligible. However, the difference with the cases using fast evaluations is not statistically
566 significant. The same occurs when comparing RandomSearch and RBFOpt with 600 function evaluations.
567 This close similarity indirectly benefits RandomSearch, as it is the simplest strategy to apply, especially
568 when there is an available parallel computing platform.

569 3.4 Insight into optimization-based model tuning results

570 The results of the optimization process yielded better learning capabilities than those of manual tuning.
571 Figure 6A shows one of the best configurations found by SurrogateOpt, the preferred method, in action,
572 and compares it to the manually tuned option. Although the manually tuned result plateaus after 400
573 seconds, the optimized result continues to improve accuracy after that point. In addition, the optimized
574 result is more reliable, as its standard deviation is smaller.

575 Of the various parameters, the most interesting are the ones that define the shape of the STDE kernels of
576 the learning rule for the neurons (MSN D1 and D2). Figure 6B shows the differences between the manually
577 tuned kernel and the optimized kernel. While the manually tuned solution tends to use asymmetrical kernels
578 in every case, it seems that the optimized solution uses symmetrical kernels for low DA and asymmetrical
579 kernels for high DA.

580 If we consider symmetrical kernels having values with equal signs and asymmetrical kernels with opposite
581 signs, this is in accordance with the values obtained by Gurney et al. (2015) in their exhaustive parametric
582 search (Figure 11 in their article). This could be relevant as they are considering more biological constraints

583 than us. The only discrepancy is in the case of high DA in MSN D2 neurons, where the optimized kernel is
 584 reversed from the range obtained by Gurney et al. However, further research is needed to better understand
 585 the significance of these findings as well as the plausibility of the proposed parameters.

Figure 6. **A.** Comparison between one of the best results obtained with the SurrogateOpt optimization method (blue) with the best manually-tuned result (orange), with the mean and standard deviation ($n = 5$). **B.** Comparison of parameters related with the STDE kernel.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

586 This study addresses the tuning of spiking neural models of striatum plasticity by using state-of-the-art
 587 black-box and surrogate optimization methods. This kind of model is useful for understanding how the
 588 brain could perform online reinforcement learning, a fundamental ability that is essential for many tasks
 589 such as motor control or decision-making. However, tuning these models is a difficult task due to the
 590 high dimensionality of the parameter space and the time required for the simulations. In addition, experts
 591 are often biased in their choices of parameter values. This problem can be addressed as an optimization
 592 problem, which can be solved using different methods.

593 This work makes a selection of optimization algorithms designed for computationally-demanding
 594 objective functions and compatible with parallel computing. The goal is to find the best alternative
 595 to avoid the necessity of tedious and expert-biased trial-and-error tuning of biologically realistic neural
 596 models that require much time to be simulated. This approach could automate model tuning despite not
 597 having been broadly studied yet in this context. Automation will not only avoid potential errors and biased
 598 configurations, but it can also reduce the required time from weeks to hours.

599 The solvers considered are SurrogateOpt, shipped with the Optimization Toolbox of Matlab, RBFOpt,
 600 which is an open-source optimizer written in Python, and DIRECT-GL, which is an improvement of
 601 a widespread optimizer written in Matlab yet open-source too. Aside from them, a naive pure-random
 602 search strategy has also been implemented. They have been compared when trying to tune a spiking neural
 603 model of striatum plasticity that takes 1.78 hours on average to be simulated in the computing platform.
 604 The methods were only allowed to evaluate 300 solutions in the first case and 600 in the second. Both

605 computational budgets are in the same order of magnitude as a human expert takes to tune the model used
606 as the benchmark, i.e., several hundred function evaluations.

607 SurrogateOpt stands out as the best solver to use, and it is hence recommended for this kind of
608 computationally demanding neural model tuning problem. It achieves the best average results with the
609 lowest standard deviation and significantly distinguishes itself from the rest. The model configurations that
610 it finds with 300 function evaluations can compete with the expert-based reference. Namely, the fitness of
611 the expert-based model tuning was 0.7216 after two months of work, and the average of SurrogateOpt is
612 0.7269 with 300 function evaluations (6 hours approximately). This average increases up to 0.7699 when
613 the method can launch 600 evaluations. However, the effectiveness of doubling the computational effort
614 could not be confirmed on average for the studied problem. Regardless, the generic recommendation made
615 is to work with the highest computational budget and multiple independent executions due to its stochastic
616 nature.

617 RBFOpt and RandomSearch, both stochastic methods too, perform significantly worse than SurrogateOpt
618 in terms of average fitness despite spending similar times. Hence, they should be only used when there is
619 no access to the referred solver. Nevertheless, the potential of RandomSearch for this kind of problem is
620 remarkable, especially when a high-performance computing platform is available. This method is trivial
621 to implement, and its performance can be significantly improved by increasing the number of evaluated
622 solutions per unit of time.

623 In contrast to the rest, DIRECT-GL, the only deterministic solver chosen, is also the worst option for
624 the problem at hand. Its parallel computing capabilities are limited by the number of promising regions
625 that the method can find. Since it does not find the best regions in the search space and finds few attractive
626 zones, the algorithm is unable to fully exploit the computing platform. These aspects make it not only the
627 solver that achieves the worst tuning configurations but also the slowest one.

628 As future work, the best-performing solver will be used to tune other neural models featuring
629 computationally demanding simulation processes. Additionally, the study might be extended as new
630 suitable methods arise.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

631 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
632 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

633 NC and AG conceived and designed the study. AG developed the neural model and manually tuned it,
634 while NC linked the model to the optimization methods selected. JA, AG, and EM did the literature
635 review concerning neural model tuning. NC, JL, and PM did the literature review regarding optimization
636 algorithms. AG, JA, and EM studied the results in terms of Neuroinformatics and checked the quality
637 of the optimization-based configurations. NC, JL, and PM analyzed and discussed the performance of
638 each optimizer. NC and AG wrote the first version of the manuscript, and JA, JL, EM, and PM revised it
639 and suggested improvements. All the authors made relevant contributions to the article and approved the
640 submitted version.

FUNDING

641 This research has been funded by the R+D+i projects RTI2018-095993-B-I00 and PID2021-123278OB-I00,
642 financed by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ and ERDF “A way to make Europe”; by the Junta de
643 Andalucía with reference P18-RT-1193 and by the University of Almería with reference UAL18-TIC-
644 A020-B. N.C. Cruz is supported by the Ministry of Economic Transformation, Industry, Knowledge and
645 Universities from the Andalusian government.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

646 This research is supported by the Spanish Grant INTSENSE (MICINN-FEDER-PID2019-109991GB-I00),
647 Regional grants Junta Andalucía-FEDER (CEREBIO P18-FR-2378). This research has also received
648 funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Framework Program under the Specific Grant Agreement No. 945539
649 (Human Brain Project SGA3). Finally, A. González-Redondo is supported by an FPU Fellowship from the
650 Spanish Ministry of Education (FPU17/04432).

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

651 The neural model used, the datasets generated, the cost functions implemented, and the optimization scripts
652 defined will be available upon acceptance. *For now, the reviewers can access this material in a zip file*
653 *attached during the upload.*

REFERENCES

- 654 Audet, C. and Hare, W. (2017). *Derivative-free and blackbox optimization*, vol. 2 (Springer)
- 655 Bhosekar, A. and Ierapetritou, M. (2018). Advances in surrogate based modeling, feasibility analysis, and
656 optimization: A review. *Computers & Chemical Engineering* 108, 250–267
- 657 Bonami, P., Biegler, L. T., Conn, A. R., Cornuéjols, G., Grossmann, I. E., Laird, C. D., et al. (2008). An
658 algorithmic framework for convex mixed integer nonlinear programs. *Discrete Optimization* 5, 186–204
- 659 Brooks, S. H. (1958). A discussion of random methods for seeking maxima. *Operations research* 6,
660 244–251
- 661 Burke, D. A., Rotstein, H. G., and Álvarez, V. A. (2017). Striatal local circuitry: a new framework for
662 lateral inhibition. *Neuron* 96, 267–284
- 663 Costa, A. and Nannicini, G. (2018). Rbfopt: an open-source library for black-box optimization with costly
664 function evaluations. *Mathematical Programming Computation* 10, 597–629
- 665 Cruz, N. C., Marín, M., Redondo, J. L., Ortigosa, E. M., and Ortigosa, P. M. (2021). A comparative study
666 of stochastic optimizers for fitting neuron models. application to the cerebellar granule cell. *Informatica*
667 32, 477–498
- 668 Cruz, N. C., Redondo, J. L., Álvarez, J. D., Berenguel, M., and Ortigosa, P. M. (2018). Optimizing the
669 heliostat field layout by applying stochastic population-based algorithms. *Informatica* 29, 21–39
- 670 Cruz, N. C., Salhi, S., Redondo, J. L., Álvarez, J. D., Berenguel, M., and Ortigosa, P. M. (2019). Design
671 of a parallel genetic algorithm for continuous and pattern-free heliostat field optimization. *Journal of*
672 *Supercomputing* 75, 1268–1283
- 673 Filatovas, E., Lančinskas, A., Kurasova, O., and Žilinskas, J. (2017). A preference-based multi-objective
674 evolutionary algorithm R-NSGA-II with stochastic local search. *Central European Journal of Operations*
675 *Research* 25, 859–878

- 676 Galindo, S. E., Toharia, P., Robles, O. D., Ros, E., Pastor, L., and Garrido, J. A. (2020). Simulation,
677 visualization and analysis tools for pattern recognition assessment with spiking neuronal networks.
678 *Neurocomputing* 400, 309–321. doi:10.1016/j.neucom.2020.02.114
- 679 García-Martínez, J. M., Garzón, E. M., Cecilia, J. M., Pérez-Sánchez, H., and Ortigosa, P. M. (2015). An
680 efficient approach for solving the hp protein folding problem based on uego. *Journal of Mathematical*
681 *Chemistry* 53, 794–806
- 682 Garrido, J. A., Luque, N. R., Tolu, S., and D'Angelo, E. (2016). Oscillation-Driven Spike-Timing
683 Dependent Plasticity Allows Multiple Overlapping Pattern Recognition in Inhibitory Interneuron
684 Networks. *International Journal of Neural Systems* 26, 1650020. doi:10.1142/S0129065716500209
- 685 Gerfen, C. R. and Surmeier, D. J. (2011). Modulation of striatal projection systems by dopamine. *Annual*
686 *review of neuroscience* 34, 441
- 687 Gerstner, W. and Kistler, W. M. (2002). *Spiking neuron models: Single neurons, populations, plasticity*
688 (Cambridge University Press)
- 689 Goldstein, H. and Healy, M. J. R. (1995). The graphical presentation of a collection of means. *Journal of*
690 *the Royal Statistical Society: Series A (Statistics in Society)* 158, 175–177
- 691 Golovin, D., Solnik, B., Moitra, S., Kochanski, G., Karro, J., and Sculley, D. (2017). Google Vizier: A
692 service for black-box optimization. In *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM SIGKDD international conference*
693 *on knowledge discovery and data mining*. 1487–1495
- 694 Gonzalez-Redondo, A., Garrido, J., Naveros Arrabal, F., Hellgren Kotaleski, J., Grillner, S., and Ros, E.
695 (2022). Reinforcement learning in a spiking neural model of striatum plasticity. Under review
- 696 Graybiel, A. M. (1998). The basal ganglia and chunking of action repertoires. *Neurobiology of Learning*
697 *and Memory* 70, 119–136. doi:https://doi.org/10.1006/nlme.1998.3843
- 698 Grillner, S., Hellgren, J., Ménard, A., Saitoh, K., and Wikström, M. A. (2005). Mechanisms for selection
699 of basic motor programs – roles for the striatum and pallidum. *Trends in Neurosciences* 28, 364–370.
700 doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2005.05.004
- 701 Gurney, K., Humphries, M. D., and Redgrave, P. (2015). A New Framework for Cortico-Striatal Plasticity:
702 Behavioural Theory Meets In Vitro Data at the Reinforcement-Action Interface. *PLoS Biology* 13,
703 e1002034. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002034
- 704 Gurney, K., Prescott, T. J., and Redgrave, P. (2001). A computational model of action selection in the basal
705 ganglia. i. a new functional anatomy. *Biological Cybernetics* 84, 401–410
- 706 Gutmann, H. M. (2001). A radial basis function method for global optimization. *Journal of global*
707 *optimization* 19, 201–227
- 708 Hikosaka, O., Takikawa, Y., and Kawagoe, R. (2000). Role of the Basal Ganglia in the Control of Purposive
709 Saccadic Eye Movements. *Physiological Reviews* 80, 953–978. doi:10.1152/physrev.2000.80.3.953
- 710 Izhikevich, E. M. (2007). Solving the distal reward problem through linkage of STDP and dopamine
711 signaling. *Cerebral Cortex* 17, 2443–2452. doi:10.1093/cercor/bhl152
- 712 Jelásity, M. (2013). Two approaches for parallelizing the uego algorithm. *Optimization Theory: Recent*
713 *Developments from Mátraháza* 59, 159
- 714 Jones, D. R. (2001). The DIRECT global optimization algorithm. In *Encyclopedia of Optimization*, eds.
715 C. A. Floudas and P. M. Pardalos (Boston: Springer). 431–440
- 716 Jones, D. R. and Martins, J. R. (2021). The direct algorithm: 25 years later. *Journal of Global Optimization*
717 79, 521–566
- 718 Jones, D. R., Perttunen, C. D., and Stuckman, B. E. (1993). Lipschitzian optimization without the lipschitz
719 constant. *Journal of optimization Theory and Applications* 79, 157–181

- 720 Liaw, R., Liang, E., Nishihara, R., Moritz, P., González, J. E., and Stoica, I. (2018). Tune: A research
721 platform for distributed model selection and training. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1807.05118*
- 722 Lindfield, G. and Penny, J. (2017). *Introduction to nature-inspired optimization* (Academic Press)
- 723 López, C. P. (2014). Optimization techniques via the optimization toolbox. In *MATLAB Optimization*
724 *Techniques* (Springer). 85–108
- 725 Marín, M., Cruz, N. C., Ortigosa, E. M., Sáez-Lara, M. J., Garrido, J. A., and Carrillo, R. R. (2021). On
726 the use of a multimodal optimizer for fitting neuron models. application to the cerebellar granule cell.
727 *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics* 15
- 728 Martínez-Álvarez, A., Crespo-Cano, R., Díaz-Tahoces, A., Cuenca-Asensi, S., Ferrández Vicente, J. M.,
729 and Fernández, E. (2016). Automatic tuning of a retina model for a cortical visual neuroprosthesis using
730 a multi-objective optimization genetic algorithm. *International Journal of Neural Systems* 26, 1650021
- 731 Masoli, S., Tognolina, M., Laforenza, U., Moccia, F., and D'Angelo, E. (2020). Parameter tuning
732 differentiates granule cell subtypes enriching transmission properties at the cerebellum input stage.
733 *Communications Biology* 3, 1–12
- 734 Masquelier, T., Hugues, E., Deco, G., and Thorpe, S. J. (2009). Oscillations, Phase-of-Firing Coding,
735 and Spike Timing-Dependent Plasticity: An Efficient Learning Scheme. *Journal of Neuroscience* 29,
736 13484–13493. doi:10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2207-09.2009
- 737 Matlab, G. O. T. (2021). User's guide (r2021b). *The MathWorks Inc*
- 738 Miller, B. R., Walker, A. G., Shah, A. S., Barton, S. J., and Rebec, G. V. (2008). Dysregulated information
739 processing by medium spiny neurons in striatum of freely behaving mouse models of huntington's
740 disease. *Journal of neurophysiology* 100, 2205–2216
- 741 Ortigosa, P., García, I., and Jelasity, M. (2001). Reliability and performance of uego, a clustering-based
742 global optimizer. *Journal of Global Optimization* 19, 265–289
- 743 Redgrave, P., Prescott, T. J. J., and Gurney, K. (1999). The basal ganglia: A vertebrate solution to the
744 selection problem? *Neuroscience* 89, 1009–1023. doi:10.1016/S0306-4522(98)00319-4
- 745 Regis, R. G. and Shoemaker, C. A. (2007). A stochastic radial basis function method for the global
746 optimization of expensive functions. *INFORMS Journal on Computing* 19, 497–509
- 747 Salhi, S. (2017). *Heuristic search: The emerging science of problem solving* (Springer)
- 748 Stehman, S. V. (1997). Selecting and interpreting measures of thematic classification accuracy. *Remote*
749 *Sensing of Environment* 62, 77–89. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-4257(97)00083-7
- 750 Storn, R. and Price, K. (1997). Differential evolution—a simple and efficient heuristic for global optimization
751 over continuous spaces. *Journal of global optimization* 11, 341–359
- 752 [Dataset] Stripinis, L. and Paulavičius, R. (2022). DGO: A new DIRECT-type MATLAB toolbox for
753 derivative-free global optimization
- 754 Stripinis, L., Paulavičius, R., and Žilinskas, J. (2018). Improved scheme for selection of potentially optimal
755 hyper-rectangles in direct. *Optimization Letters* 12, 1699–1712
- 756 Sullivan, L. M. (2008). *Essentials of biostatistics workbook: statistical computing using Excel* (Jones &
757 Bartlett Learning)
- 758 Sutton, R. S., Barto, A. G., and Williams, R. J. (1992). Reinforcement learning is direct adaptive optimal
759 control. *IEEE Control Systems Magazine* 12, 19–22
- 760 Tomkins, A., Vasilaki, E., Beste, C., Gurney, K., and Humphries, M. D. (2014). Transient and steady-state
761 selection in the striatal microcircuit. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience* 7, 192. doi:10.3389/
762 fncom.2013.00192
- 763 Trobec, R., Slivnik, B., Bulić, P., and Robič, B. (2018). *Introduction to parallel computing: from algorithms*
764 *to programming on state-of-the-art platforms* (Springer)

- 765 Van Geit, W., Achard, P., and De Schutter, E. (2007). Neurofitter: a parameter tuning package for a wide
766 range of electrophysiological neuron models. *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics* 1, 1
- 767 Van Geit, W., De Schutter, E., and Achard, P. (2008). Automated neuron model optimization techniques: a
768 review. *Biological Cybernetics* 99, 241–251
- 769 Vu, K. K., d'Ambrosio, C., Hamadi, Y., and Liberti, L. (2017). Surrogate-based methods for black-box
770 optimization. *International Transactions in Operational Research* 24, 393–424
- 771 Wächter, A. and Biegler, L. T. (2006). On the implementation of an interior-point filter line-search
772 algorithm for large-scale nonlinear programming. *Mathematical Programming* 106, 25–57

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

773 Neuron models and parameters used

774 We used conductance-based versions of the Leaky-Integrate and Fire (LIF) neuron model (Gerstner
775 and Kistler, 2002) in every layer of the network, but with different parameters. We classify the neuron
776 types according to the layer they belong to: cortical neurons for the input, striatal neurons for the learning
777 layer, and action neurons for the output. There is also a dopaminergic neuron that receives the rewards and
778 punishments.

779 The parameters used for each type were manually tuned to obtain reasonable firing rates. For the cortical
780 neurons we used a number of spikes per input cycle (with 8 cycles per second) close to Masquelier et al.
781 (2009) and Garrido et al. (2016). For the striatal neurons, we tuned the parameters to obtain a mean firing
782 rate of around one spike per second to be within biological ranges (Miller et al., 2008) but with activity
783 peaks of two or three spikes per input cycle (16-24 spikes per second). The action neurons are tuned to fire
784 every input cycle if they receive enough stimulation from its channel (at least two more spikes from D1
785 neurons than D2 neurons each cycle). The dopamine neuron was tuned to have a firing range from 50 to
786 350 spikes per second. The parameters used for each neuron type are shown at supplementary Table 4.

Parameter	Cortical	Striatal	Action	Dopaminergic
e_{exc} (mV)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
e_{inh} (mV)	-85.0	-85.0	-85.0	-85.0
τ_{AMPA} (ms)	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
τ_{GABA} (ms)	10.0	30.0	60.0	10.0
τ_{ref} (ms)	1.0	15.0	15.0	1.0
C_m (pF)	250.0	50.0	100.0	250.0
g_{leak} (nS)	25.0	10.0	25.0	25.0
V_{thr} (mV)	-40.0	-50.0	-40.0	-65.0
e_{leak} (mV)	-65.0	-65.0	-65.0	-40.0

Table 4. Neuron parameters used in the model.